

THE ADVANTAGE OF DESIGNING CHILDREN'S MULTIFUNCTIONAL CLOTHING IN A TRANSFORMATION WAY

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Abstract:The article is devoted to the question of the advantage of designing children's clothing in the transformation method, and the requirements for multifunctional children's clothing and the transformation method were studied. Transformatively designed children's clothing is the future of the manufacturing industry and today's modern fashion trend highlights the importance of transformation in not only adult but also children's clothing.

Key words: transformation, multifunctional children's clothing, design, project.

Today, reforms are being carried out in the field of light industry in our Republic, and production enterprises are being equipped with modern equipment, as a result of which work efficiency increases and product quality meets the requirements of the world market. Despite the fact that the children's clothing industry is developing, there are still many unsolved problems. Taking into account such shortcomings, the authors aimed to find a solution to the problems encountered in children's seasonal clothes between 3-6 years of age. It is known that children between 3-6 years of age are active, growing rapidly, and are very sensitive to rapid weather changes in the spring- autumn season. In order to find a solution to the above problems, it was proposed to develop a project of multifunctional children's clothing using the transformation method.

Transformation is- (lat. Transformation- change)- changing the goal direction of activity, changing structures, forms and methods; or the change, appearance, form, essential characteristics of something change. Similar words

mean change, change, demonstration, revolution, rebirth, repackaging [1].

The most common definition of the term "transformation" is as follows: "transformation is a change in the form, appearance, essential properties of something" [2-3-4]. Considering this term as a part of clothing design, we have the following definition: "transformation is the property of changing the original forms and parameters of objects of the object- spatial world in the process of existence or operation" [5-6]

Changeable things, especially clothes, have been around for a long time. Information about various transformation options can be found in the technical literature of a wide range of knowledge and sciences[7-8]. These data allow us to assume that the design of objects with a design capable of modification is one of the trends in the development of costume design. This trend is also related to providing many functions of human life.

Hussain Chalayan (Great Britain), Jane Chan (Jane Chung), Blessus (Poland) brand are constantly operating in this direction. The suit has a number of techniques that provide transformation: stretching- squeezing; extraction- combination; orientation- fixation (fixation); folding (closing)- unfolding); disappear (hide)- appear; detailed replacement; replacement[9].

Along with the techniques and methods of transforming transformed garments, there are various principles of transformation that are important in shaping. These principles of clothing transformation allow systematization of various design details in the form of initial transformations. For example, transformation principles can include:

1. The principle of converting one shape into another (for example, changing the length of a product, converting one element of a suit into another (headwear into a bag, etc.).

2. The principle of changing details within one product form (for example, clothes a elements are changed (folded, folded, tied, braided, etc.) In general, changing clothes (and its individual elements) - the process of changing can be

many. There are positive moments in this process, because the manufactured product does not allow to be disturbed due to its variety and versatility, and therefore its wearing time is extended.

Modern fashion designers, based on the techniques and principles of the design of variable clothes, offered a unique answer to the economic crisis that forced consumers to save on clothes: for example, "multifunctional" models that can be transformed from a coat into a jacket, etc. from skirt to skirt. The question of the use of transformation in school clothes is relevant for two reasons: the active physiological growth of the student and the need for various equipment of the student's wardrobe [8]

In the development of our proposed model for children of kindergarten age, children's active physical movement, clothing construction, physical mechanical properties as a result of active movement, and hygienic indicators were taken into account. Also, children's clothes serve to attract children's attention with their aesthetic indicators, material quality, color harmony, texture, decoration and decorative pictures. Silhouette and shape are important in children's clothing. It is necessary to maintain its structure, movement, breathing and blood circulation in the body. Children's outerwear should be warm, light and, most importantly, should serve the child's free movement. Tight and tightly fitting clothes not only resist the child's freedom of movement, but also cause a deterioration in mood [10].

As a result, young growing children have a negative effect on the nervous system, causing them to become capricious. In addition, blood circulation as a result of resistance to free movement and in some cases blood vessel constriction may also cause problems in the system. In the model we propose, taking into account the above aspects, when designing children's multi- functional seasonal clothes, in the climate of our country, as a result of frequent changes in air temperature during the seasons, more children catch colds. Kindergarten children die very quickly sib causes their clothes to not fit their body size, resulting in their

clothes becoming small in one season. The difference of our new design outerwear for children from the existing ones is that it is designed for three seasons of the year: spring, autumn and winter using the transformation method, and as a result of the transformation, our proposed model can be used as 4 different clothing assortments, that is, sleeves and pants with the help of special fittings. part is removed, as a result, according to the consumer's choice, it can be used in combination with other types of clothes by attaching a belt to the trousers. This makes it easier for children to wear and take off, to use with other types of clothes, and for parents, it is more convenient from the economic point of view. As a solution to these problems, we used the transformation method in the design of children's multifunctional clothing (Fig. 1)

"ASALARI" was selected as a creative source for our proposal model, without departing from the chosen topic (Fig. 2). The main reason for choosing bees as a creative source is that bees are hardworking and live together as a family, which is educational for children and attracts children's attention with their bright colors. Bees from our selected creative resource were used as decoration for children's outerwear, which is being artistically designed. Beehive shape was chosen for shells used as decoration on outerwear.

Figure 1. The main offer is the model

Figure 2. Image selected as creative resource.

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